

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ARANGO LONDONO****FIRST NAME: MARIA****PROGRAM CODE: MDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

ACADEMIC WRITING TIPS

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic essay writing involves persuasion. A good piece of writing has the ability to pose a question, provide evidence on said question and support the proposed answer. In order to produce an accepted piece, rules need to be followed and applied. However, within those rules I found that a writer still has a big playing field. In Chapter 1 to 6 of the *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, we as new writers are shown and explained the fundamentals to a well-executed academic article. Before one can get started, there are three fundamental steps that need to be done. The planification of the piece, choosing a writing style and understanding the rules of the language in which you are writing. By following the three following points a writer is able to produce enough evidence, create a proper outline, produce a well cited and clear paper as well as one that is grammatically correct.

2) THE PROCESS

Writing is a form of intellectual art. The complexity of the task, with the rules and components associated with it, make for the ability to understand, address, analysis, and elaborate possible. When looking at academic writing, one must first establish the question that will be addresses as well as whom the intended audience is. Once this is established, I find that the capacity to gather evidence and formulate a persuasive argument will quickly unfold. The central component to any essay comes from answering the question posed by the author (EUCLID 2019, 1.). Writing is not a linear process. It is a progression of your thoughts and ideas, research as well as the ability to bring it all together (EUCLID 2019, 1).

Due to the high amount of time it takes to fully develop a breakdown of an essay, it makes sense to me that one should start not only writing but reading early. By doing so, people have the ability to become comfortable and familiar with their topic of discussion. I find that it is essential to fully research a specific topic, that way not only will the evidence compiled come from different sources but it is very probable that the writer will encounter over views.

When writing, especially an article that is meant to persuade a reader, both sides of the argument must be explored (EUCLID 2019, 2). You will not only have a better rounder paper but the credibility behind it will increase. An important suggestion that I found very useful was “Try to get ‘inside’ the conception you are discussing” (EUCLID 2019, 15). The ability to think outside your own thoughts and understand why other people have the opposing view, will allow you to really break part the discussion or evidence in a way that will increase your argument. This is what I think the author was getting at when discussing creative vs critical thinking. You have to use both forms of thinking. Creative, gives the writer the ability to expand their ideas, while the critical thought, allows for the narrowing of them (EUCLID 2019, 2). Despite both ways of thought seeming opposite to one another, they are both needed in writing. When drafting an essay, the questions *how* and *which* should be constantly used. Answering *how* the question will be answer, *which* evidence will support *which* and *how* sub-argument (EUCLID 2019, 14), for me, I found to be fundamental in starting the drafting processes.

As discussed above, there are rules to writing. These are found in the style formats of writing. Examples are MLA, APA, Oxford, Turabian (Recommended by EUCLID) etc. These are set up for the writing to be consistent. There are multiple styles that a writer can pick from as they are set up for different forms of writing (EUCLID 2019, 24). Within their structures the citing processes is addressed.

3) THE RULES

The rules of writing are consistent throughout the writing process; however, I find very important to note, that a writer needs to be very vigilant in what style they are writing in. Each writing style has different ways to quote and cite information. If the rules within the styles are not followed, it leaves room for plagiarism. Plagiarism is the writing of information where the writer of said information is not given the appropriate credit (EUCLID 2019, 5); nonetheless, it is important to state that even if something is said by that author and it is used in the text and not quoted but is common knowledge, then not citing is appropriate (Ibid.). I think that as long as the writer follows the rules of the styles they will not have any issues. They will know which ones require footnotes vs in-text citations, how the work cited or bibliography needs to be structured etc. Citation styles as well as how to use quotations depending on the length, are also found within those style guides. For example, long quotations will become their own paraphrase but with different spacing and font size within the article (EUCLID 2019, 5-12). Overall, referencing is essential to any writing. Not only will it allow others to find where the evidence to your argument comes from, but also gives credit where it is due and keeps the writing clean.

4) THE LANGUAGES

A writer works within a given amount of space. Therefore, words need to be chosen carefully and they need to be able to identify and omit words that are unnecessary to their writing (EUCLID 2019, 17-23). The English language needs to be written carefully, as there are many words that sound the same but have different meanings when used. Same goes for different English language speaking countries. The American and British English are similar in many ways but are inherently different when it comes to their pronunciation, spelling, grammar and general usage (EUCLID 2019, 27-29).

Examples of different English uses, with the same meaning but differently written:

- United States English:
 - “England has (...) played well today, even if it lost” (EUCLID 2019, 29)
- British English:
 - “England have played well today, even if they lost” (Ibid.)
- Canadian English:
 - England played well today, even if they lost

This text did not mention Canadian English; however, I believe it should be mentioned because that is the English I grew up studying. Overall, the English language does have the same concepts and writer and reader and able to understand each text; however, different terms and expressions are often used (EUCLID 2019, 30-34).

5) CONCLUSION

In academic writing there are multiple variables to consider. A proper collection of evidence exploring the subject from both sides, as well as the ability to plan are vital to a successful article. However, the writing style is equally as important. Due to the amount of writing styles, the writer has the ability to pick the style that is best suited to how they want to express their research. The style also provides the foundation for a paper to be properly cited, which ultimately helps avoid plagiarism. Lastly, understanding the English language. United States English vs British English have multiple differences that need to be acknowledged. However, it is also important to realize that despite them being the two discussed, English in countries like Canada also vary in how their grammar is structured. For me overall, I found the despite their being rules to follow, there is flexibility between the work. The hardest point for myself to implement in my writing will be the U.S grammar rules and spelling. Nonetheless, breaking the coursepack down into three main sections allowed myself to simplify it in order to then have it be used for any form of writing.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

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